

2015

APR-MAY

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : I I I

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

**A STUDY ON TEACHERS' VIEWPOINTS TOWARDS GUIDANCE AND
COUNSELING SERVICES IN TEHRAN'S HIGH SCHOOLS**

Sima Joneydi

Research Scholar,

Department of Education & Extension,

University of Pune

Under the Supervising of **Dr. Lalita Vartak**

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to study the counseling services, given to high schools' students from teachers' viewpoints as one of the main stakeholders of the services. Participants were 110 teachers. A researcher-designed survey questionnaire based on three main domains counseling services including Educational, personal-social and vocational in high schools, and some necessary demographic and primary information included Teacher's attitude towards counselor, guidance and counseling services, was used for data analysis. SPSS was used to code and analysis the collected data, producing descriptive statistics included frequency, mean, standard deviation and correlation: and also producing inferential statistic included one sample t-Test. Results showed that teachers have positive attitude towards the services in general and in two main domains(personal-social and vocational) but their viewpoints towards the services in educational domain are negative. 85% of participations emphasized on the necessity of counseling and guidance program in all three main domains of guidance and counseling services.

Key Words: *Counseling and Guidance Services, counselor*

(SGC is an abbreviation of School Guidance and Counseling)

Introduction

Guidance and Counseling : Guidance and Counseling has a rather long history in Iran's educational system more than 150 years. But officially and systematically It started with

establishing "Darolfonoon" as the first Technical school, in 1949. A brief history SGC services in Iran:

(Saafi,2009)

Process of guidance and counseling has specific position in education system especially in secondary course, because it directly involves achieving its most prominent responsibility that is: " training human beings as hale and hearty citizens and requisite human resource", and in fact it is a facilitating mean for achieving the education goals. (Pasha sharifi, 1994).

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

**(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655**

A rapidly changing work world and labor force; violence in homes, school and communities; divorce; teenage suicide; substance abuse; and sexual experimentations are just a few examples of these challenges. These challenges are real and they are having extensive impact on the personal/social, career, and academic development of the children and young people (Gysbers, 1999).

Scholars in the field urge that comprehensive guidance and counseling programs are effective in assisting children and young people, ...to respond to these and similar challenges. It is believed that when school counselors have time, resources and the structure of a comprehensive program to work in, good things happen, that is, guidance counseling interventions improve academic achievement, students take more demanding courses, students develop and use career plans, and school have more positive climates (Day, 2004). Therefore, surveying, supervising and evaluating every components and activities of the process of SGC. services, through systematic researches, is essential and has a particular importance in achieving the aims of education system. The beneficiaries of the program are one of the most important groups to evaluate the program's services. Not many studies have been conducted regarding teacher's perceptions of the responsibilities of school counselors (Beesley 2004; Clark and Amatea, 2004), and most of the ones that have been done emphasized teacher-counselor collaboration rather than teacher's insight about specific school counselor duties (Reiner, Colbert, & Pérusse, 2009). White (1998), Kaufman, Klein, & Frase (1999) reported the remarkable impact of the SGCs. on decreasing dropout rates. and Iran as well Sorour Mojgan 1980, Bakhshipoor joibari, 1994, Moshkbid Haghghi 1994, . (Stokes, 1997). Quast (2003), 1999, Scruggs Kottman and Wilborn (1992) Curcio, Mathai, and Robert (2003) . While they are one of the important ring of the chain who involved in the program and services directly and indirectly. So, this study tried to pay attention to teachers' views towards SGC services.

Statement of the problem

Study of the given SGC services to Tehran's high schools' teachers for helping their students in three main domains including Education, Personal-Social adjustment and Vocation

Assumptions of the Study

The counseling services play an important role in educational system as a guide and facilitator which lead it to the shortest way to achieve its goals.

The SGC services affects remarkably on distributing competent human resources of the society.

Operational Definition

Guidance: In this study Guidance services are considered as all a process of assisting students, individuals to help themselves through their own efforts, to discover and to develop their potential resources for personal fulfillment and social usefulness.

Counseling: In this study, Counseling services are considered as all activities, techniques, advices and information which are used and offered by counselors in Tehran's high schools to help students in three main domains of development, including: Educational, Personal-Social and Vocational.

d. Major Service Areas

The major service areas of guidance and counseling include:

1. Educational guidance and counseling

Educational guidance is so far as it can be distinguished from any other form of guidance. It is concerned with the provision of assistance to pupils in their choices in adjustment to the schools' curriculum and school life in general. Educational guidance is therefore essential in counseling service. Guiding young people to pursue the right type of education in which, for example the right balance is met for accommodating the human resource needs of a nation.

This aspect of counseling should concern itself with assisting the students in their curriculum and school life choices. Students need assistance in choosing subject and planning for the courses which they take at these institutions of higher learning. All lecturers could be involved in this without any need for specialized training in counseling.

2. Personal and social guidance and counseling

Personal and social guidance is the process of helping an individual on how to behave with consideration to other people. Primarily, personal and social guidance helps the individual to understand her/himself, how to get along with others, manners and etiquette, leisure time

activities, social skills, family and family relationships and understanding masculine and feminine roles.

This aspect of counseling refers to the very personal problems that students meet. These problems may range from financial needs to interpersonal relationships. Although the lecturers may help to reduce these pressures, there is need for more specialized assistance from professionally trained hands. The fact that the lecturers may have an upper hand in interaction with the students only goes to show how crucial it is that they should get involved. As role models to the majority of students it is important the lectures are made aware of their crucial role in social guidance.

3. Vocational guidance and counseling

Vocational guidance is a process of helping individuals to choose an occupation, prepare for, enter into and progress in it. Vocational satisfaction requires that a person's interests, aptitudes and personality be suitable for his/her work. It plays its part by providing individuals with a comprehension of the world of work and essential human needs, thus familiarizing individuals with such terms as 'dignity of labor' and 'work value'.

This aspect of counseling addresses the learners' problems as regards to vocational choices. Again here the lecturers are best placed to give relevant advice to learners since they know their academic strengths and weaknesses in areas that may pertain to specific vocations, occupations or jobs. The fact that the lecturers know the interests and aptitudes of most of their students makes them the best persons to assist their students in areas that are related to their vocations.

Counseling Techniques

On the basis of the nature of the counseling process and the part of the counselor, three techniques are used:

- 1. Directive perspective or counselor-centered counseling**
- 2. Non-directive, Permissive or Client-Centered Counseling**
- 3. Eclectic Counseling**

which can be offered in individual or group counseling.

Counseling Process

(Hackney& Cormier, 1996)

Research Questions

Following are the questions:

- 1) What is the attitude of teachers towards the SGC services given in educational domain to their children in Tehran's high schools?
- 2) What is the attitude of teachers towards the SGC services given in personal-social domain to their children in Tehran's high schools?
- 3) What is the attitude of the teachers towards the SGC services given in vocational domain to their children in Tehran's high schools?

Hypothesis

H₁. Attitude of teachers towards the given SGC services in Tehran high schools is positive.

NH₁. Attitude of teachers towards the given SGC services in Tehran high schools is not positive.

Methodology

As survey is the most appropriate for obtaining factual or attitudinal information or for research questions about self-reported beliefs, opinions, values, motives, ideas, habits, feelings, desires, characteristics and present or past behavior (David & Sutton 2004; Gray 2004), to obtain teachers viewpoints about SGC services in Tehran's high schools, survey has been conducted.

Sampling

For selecting the teachers' participants of the study convenience sampling was used. Convenient sampling refers to the collection of information from members of the population who are conveniently available to provide it (Sekaran, 2008).

Deciding the Sample Size

The sample of the study consists of those teachers who volunteer to participate in the study. Therefore, 110 teachers from 3 districts (6, 7, 18) out of 19 districts of Tehran, considering different social-economic and cultural context of the city, were selected, conveniently, as the sample of the study.

Tool

For the purposes of this study, two methods were used to gather data required to answer the research hypotheses: (a) related literature review, (b) self-developed survey instruments. For this purpose, a questionnaire was developed by the researcher to address the research hypotheses and to study the relations of number of variables, 1- attitude 2- Educational, 3- Personal-social 4-Vocational.

Validity of the tool

To assess the content validity of the questionnaires, two procedures were used: (1) a group of experts was asked to review the questionnaire and provide feedback on content relevance and clarity, 2) a pilot test of instrument was administered to 10% of participants similar to those who participated in the study.

Reliability of the tool

For the purpose of this study, Cronbach Alpha was calculated to ensure reliability of the questionnaire. The calculated Cronbach Alpha is 0.937

D.Data Analysis And Interpretation Of The Collected Data.

Tools for Data Analysis

Data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 19 and EXCEL. The following statistics was used to analyze the data:

- By using descriptive statistics, frequencies were tabulated and compared to indicate the teachers' viewpoints towards SGC services.
- One sample t-test was used to identify the satisfactory of SGC services from the viewpoint of teachers

Observations:

The results of the table No.1 indicates the calculated Skewness and kurtosis for teachers' attitude towards SGC services yield between ± 2 , therefore it can be assumed that the distribution of the teachers viewpoints is approximately normal.

Based on the results of Tables No.2 & No.3 :

Performing One Sample t-Test to investigate the Satisfaction of Counseling Service based on teachers views indicates:

Attitude: The calculated t ($t=-3.70$, $df=109$, $p<0.05$) for teachers' attitude about SGCs. is more than the table t-value ($t=1.96$, $p<0.05$). (Table 3)

Interpretation: Therefore, the hypothesis (H_1) regarding to the teachers attitude to SGCs. is accepted at the 95% confidence level. In fact teachers' attitude about SGCs. is positive.

Educational: The calculated t ($t=-1.126$ $df=109$, $p<0.05$) for teachers' viewpoints towards educational SGCs. is less than table t-value ($t=1.96$, $p<0.05$). (Table 3). Therefore, the hypothesis (H_1) regarding to the satisfactory of SGCs.in educational Domain is rejected at the 95% confidence level. In fact from teachers' viewpoints, educational SGCs. are not satisfactory.

Personal-Social: The calculated t ($t=-3.693$ $df=109$, $p<0.05$) for teachers' viewpoints towards SGCs. in Personal-social adjustment is less than table t-value ($t=1.96$, $p<0.05$). (Table 3). Therefore, the hypothesis (H_1) regarding to the satisfactory of SGCs. in personal-social adjustment is accepted at the 95% confidence level. In fact from teachers' viewpoints, personal-social SGCs. are satisfactory.

Vocational: The calculated t ($t=-2.027$ $df=109$, $p<0.05$) for teachers' viewpoints towards vocational SGCs. is more than table t-value ($t=1.96$, $p<0.05$). (Table 3). Therefore, the hypothesis (H_1) regarding to the satisfactory of vocational SGCs. is accepted at the 95% confidence level. In fact from teachers' viewpoints vocational SGCs. are satisfactory.

Table No.4 reflects the teachers’ responses on the question “do u think guidance & counseling program in high school is necessary?” More than 85% emphasized on the necessity of guidance and counseling program in high school.

Conclusion and Discussion

The results of the all observations above shows teachers’ attitude towards current SGC services is positive, in personal-social, vocational & also in general but in educational domain their viewpoint is negative. 85% of them, also emphasis on the necessity of SGC. program in high schools and full-time presence of counselors in high schools. These findings are in a remarkable alignment with the few numbers of previous research: Moshkbid Haghighi,1995, Sorour Mojgan, 1980,Atyabi,1979, has also found that 88% of students and 92% of teachers emphasized on the necessity of counselor presence and SGC services. Based on the finding of the two theses authors (Quast, 2003; Stokes, 1997), it would appear parents in these school districts studies felt elementary and high school counselors provided services essential to their child(ren)'s school success.

Table No.1 Descriptive Statistics: Teachers’Attitude Towards SGC services in general & 3 main domain.

		Attitude	Educational	Personal-	Vocational
N	Valid	110	110	110	110
Mean		3.66	3.92	3.67	3.83
Std.		.093	.074	.089	.085
Std.		.970	.774	.938	.894
Variance		.941	.600	.880	.799
Skewness		-1.51	-1.02	-1.29	-1.25
Std.		.230	.230	.230	.230
Kurtosis		2.80	1.22	2.20	1.79
Std.Error		.457	.457	.457	.457
Range		4.64	3.71	4.44	4.00
Sum		402.36	430.86	403.67	421.00

Table No.2 Descriptive statistics of Teachers' Attitude Towards SGC services in general & 3 main domains

One-Sample Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Attitude	110	3.66	.970	.093	
Educational	110	3.92	.774	.074	
Personal-	110	3.67	.938	.089	
Vocational	110	3.83	.894	.085	

Table No.3 One Sample t-Test Teachers' Attitude Towards SGC services in general & 3 main domains

One-Sample Test							
Test Value = 2							
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Lower	95% Confidence Upper	
Attitude	-3.70	109	.000	-.34	-.53	-.16	
Educational	-1.13	109	.263	-.083	-.230	.063	
Personal-	-3.69	109	.000	-.330	-.508	-	
Vocational	-2.03	109	.045	-.173	-.342	-	

Table No.4 Necessity of Counseling Programs in High School based on teachers' viewpoints

Do you think guidance & counseling program in high school is necessary?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
Valid	No Answer	2	0.2	0.2	0.2
	So hcum	56	50.1	50.1	50.3
	Much	39	35.5	35.5	85.8
	So so about 50%	11	10.0	10.0	95.8
	Somewhat	2	0.2	0.2	100.0
	Total	110	100.0	100.0	

References

Atyabi, H. and Others,(1979), A Study on Counseling Services in Guidance Schools from different stakeholders grups(students, teachers, counselors, administrators) MA thesis, Tarbiat Malem University, Tehran.

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

- Bakhshipoor, P. (1995), A Study on Counselors effectiveness in Tehran from Administrator, Students and Parents' views, MA Thesis , Tehran.
- Best, J. W. Kahn, James V. "Research in Education" 7th ed. New Delhi: Asoke K., 2004.
- Day, S. X., 2004. Theory and Design in Counseling and Psychotherapy. Boston, NY: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Cochran, W. G. (1963). Sampling Techniques, 2nd Edition, NewYork: John Wiley and Sons.
- Curcio, C.C., Mathai, C.R., & Roberts, I. (2003). Evaluation of a school district's secondary counseling program. *Professional School Counseling*,
- David,M. &Sutton, C. D.(2004)Social Research: The Basic London, Sage Publication.
- Garrett, E Henry, "Statistics in Psychology and Education" 10th Indian reprint, 1981.
- Gray,D.F. (2004),Doing Research in The Real World, New Delhi, Sage Publication.
- Haghighi, Moshkbid,(1994),A Study on the Students, Parents and Administrators' expectations from counselor, MA thesis, Allame TabaTabai University, Tehran.
- Hosseini Mehdi , principles and methods if guidance and counseling , Azad university publications, Tehran 1991
- Gysbers N.C. (1999). Strengthening Guidance Leadership for the 21st Century.
- Kaufman, P., Klein, S., & Frase, M. (1999). Dropout Rates in the United States, 1997.Statistical Analysis Report. U.S. Department of Education.
- Navabi nejad shokouh, guidance and counseling, moaser pub. Tehran1995)
- Norcross , J.C strausse , D.J. , & Missar, C.D. (1988) The process and outcomes of psycho therapists' personal treatment experiences psychotherapy, 25 , 36 – 43.
- Norcross ,J.C (Ed.)(1987b) special section: Toward a common language foe psychotherapy . Journal of Integrative & Eclective psychotherapy.

Copyrights @ **Sima Joneydi & Dr. Lalita Vartak**..This is an open access peer reviewed article distributed under the creative common attribution license which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provide the original work is cited.